

STRENGTHENING CLINICAL TRIAL REGULATORY AND ETHICAL REVIEW OVERSIGHT IN EAST AFRICA.

D 2.6 Publish Summarized evaluation reports of clinical trial applications

Project acronym: ACCESSAFRICA 2

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Deliverable factsheet:

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1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	Uganda National Health Research Organisation	UNHRO	Uganda
3.	Partner	Jimma University	JU	Ethiopia
4.	Partner	Uganda National Council for Science and Technology	UNCST	Uganda
5.	Partner	National Drug Authority	NDA	Uganda

BACKGROUND

The National Drug Authority (NDA) approves clinical trials based on an assessment of the information provided in a clinical trial application (CTA), focusing primarily on the risks and benefits of the investigational product. Assessment reports serve as an objective evaluation tool and form the basis of the regulatory decision. However, these reports were not easily accessible to applicants or the public. To improve transparency and accessibility of clinical trial information in Uganda, the Access Africa 2 project under work page 2 supported NDA in publishing summarized evaluation reports of CTAs as a means of providing concise information to researchers and the public.

Objective

To ensure that key findings and decisions from clinical trial evaluations are provided in easy to understand summaries.

Methodology

The Access Africa 2 project supported the National Drug Authority (NDA) in adopting the structured African Vaccine Regulatory Forum (AVAREF) evaluation tool for clinical trials. Using this tool, a structured template was created to summarize evaluation information, to ensure consistency in the published data. The template is then filled with specific evaluation details from each CTA and published on the NDA website at <http://nda.or.ug/> under the Directorate of Product Safety. Reports can be accessed and downloaded from this site.

This deliverable was included in the newly amended National Drug Policy and Authority (Conduct of Clinical Trials) Regulations, 2024, under Regulation 8, Sub-Regulation 4, which states, "The Authority shall publish summary evaluation reports of applications to conduct clinical trials."

(g) the objectives of the clinical trial will not be achieved; or

(h) it is not in the public interest to authorise the clinical trial.

(4) The Authority shall publish summary evaluation reports of applications to conduct clinical trials.

(5) The Authority will make its own regulatory decisions when considering external reports, recommendations and communications on clinical trials' applications taking place in Uganda

9. Clinical trial Certificate.
A clinical trial certificate shall—

Figure 1: Excerpt of the newly amended NDA clinical trial regulations to support publication of summarized evaluation reports

Some of the initial CTAs that were published are listed below

CTA code	Title
TBTC Study (CTA 0262)	Six weeks of daily rifapentine vs. a comparator arm of 12-16 week rifamycin-based treatment of latent M. tuberculosis infection: assessment of safety, tolerability and effectiveness
CTA 0259	Optimizing the Dose of Flucytosine for the Treatment of Cryptococcal Meningitis
CTA 0245	Intramuscular vs. Enteral Penicillin Prophylaxis to Prevent Progression of Latent Rheumatic Heart Disease: A non-inferiority randomized trial

Below is a copy of the summary evaluation report for CTA 0259 that was published

Study Title: *Optimizing the Dose of Flucytosine for the Treatment of Cryptococcal Meningitis*
NDA CTA Number: 0259
Protocol No. NA
Version No. 1.1
Date: 14 August 2023

National Principal Investigator (NPI): Associate Prof. David Meya
Institution /Trial Site: Infectious Diseases Institute/Kiruddu National Referral Hospital & Mbarara Regional Referral Hospital
Sponsor: Makerere University Lung Institute-MakNCD Program
REC of Record: IDI REC
REC Reference number: IDI-REC-2022-32
UNCST Refence Number: HS2940ES
NDA date of Approval: 19th March 2024

Study Background and Rationale

CM has emerged as one of the most frequent and deadly opportunistic infections in HIV patients with a global burden estimated at nearly 1 million cases annually. 5-FC is essential in reducing fungal burden in the first week of therapy but access remains limited in settings with CM incidence.

In a randomized clinical trial using a higher dose of amphotericin (0.7mg/kg/day) with or without 5-FC (100mg/kg/day), addition of 5FC resulted in higher rates of CSF sterilization and lower mortality rates and no difference in toxicity between groups. The dose was selected as an attempt to mitigate toxicity and maximize therapeutic effects and not based on systematic analysis.

Preliminary modelling based on AMBITION Pharmacokinetics demonstrated that 5-FC may reach concentrations above MIC for *Cryptococcus* even at lower and less frequent dosing. Data suggests the dose of 5-FC can be safely adjusted for optimization while maintaining the mortality benefit of CM induction therapy.

Studies have shown that 5-FC can be used effectively at 100mg/kg/day, no studies have shown if lower doses might be effective, and this can have an impact on access by reducing the cost and supplies needed for CM patients.

Primary Objectives and Outcome Measures

To demonstrate the reduced dose of 5-FC, when combined with IV AMB for induction therapy of CM is non-inferior compared to traditional dosing of 5-FC in reducing fungal burden of *Cryptococcus*.

Primary endpoint.

- CSF early fungicidal activity (EFA) during induction treatment: as measured in the change in log₁₀ CFU/mL of CSF/day and as assessed with general linear models. EFA from the intervention group will be compared to historical controls of fluconazole monotherapy, of fluconazole + flucytosine, of IV amphotericin + fluconazole, and of IV liposomal amphotericin (single-dose) + flucytosine (100 mg/kg/day) + fluconazole (1200 mg/day) or IV deoxycholate amphotericin + flucytosine (100 mg/kg/day).

- Laboratory anomalies (Grade 2-5 adverse events) and Clinical Adverse Reactions (Grade 3-5) as per the NIAID DAIDS toxicity grading table will be separately compared between the flucytosine group and the historical controls for the frequency of having at least one event and the mean number of events with linear and logistic regression models.

Secondary Objectives and Outcome Measures

- To determine if there remains a mortality benefit to 5-FC for induction therapy at reduced dosing.
- To assess the overall safety and tolerability of 5-FC at reduced dosing

Secondary endpoints

Desirability of Outcome Response (DOOR) as ordinal ranked maximum score tested by Win Ratio.

- 18-week Survival with CSF sterility by 2-weeks
- 18-week survival with CSF culture positivity beyond 2 weeks
- Grade 3 hematological adverse event by 2 weeks
- Grade 4 hematological adverse event by 2 weeks
- Lost to follow up before 18-weeks
- Serious Adverse Event through 18 weeks (e.g. all-cause re-hospitalization, permanent neurologic deficit)
- Death by 18-weeks

CSF culture sterility cumulative incidence over 18 weeks

18-week survival time

Study Design

It's a prospective, adaptive, non-inferiority, open-label, trial to compare the efficacy and safety of reduced dosing of 5-FC induction therapy for the treatment of cryptococcal meningitis in combination with IV AMB to standard of care, with EFA as the primary endpoint.

Study Population

Participants >18 years with Cerebrospinal Fluid cryptococcal antigen (CrAg) positive meningitis

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- CSF cryptococcal antigen (CrAg) positive meningitis Ability and willingness to provide informed consent. Willing to receive protocol-specified lumbar punctures

Exclusion Criteria:

- Age < 18 years
- Inability to take enteral (oral or nasogastric) medicine
- Cannot or unlikely to attend regular clinic visits
- Receiving chemotherapy or corticosteroids
- Suspected paradoxical immune reconstitution inflammatory syndrome (IRIS)
- Pregnancy or breastfeeding (tested on screening)
- CrCl < 20 mL/minute
- White blood cell count < 1.5 cells/ μ L
- Patients with prior 5-flucytosine exposure >3 days in the prior year
- Any condition for which participation would not be in the best interest of the participant or that could limit protocol specified assessments.

Target Trial Duration including Follow-Up period

12 months

Investigational Medicinal Product

Oral flucytosine 60mg/kg/day three times a day for 10 days

Study Arms

- The investigational cohort will receive 60mg/kg/day of Flucytosine divided into 3 doses per day for 10 days, n=36 CSF culture positive.
- The control group will consist of matched historical participants in the AMBITION trial
- All participants will receive liposomal Amphotericin B 10 mg/kg, single-dose infusion, if available.
- If liposomal Amphotericin is unavailable, participants will receive IV amphotericin deoxycholate 0.7-1.0 mg/kg/day for 7 days.

Sample size

50 participants

Evaluator's Risk/Benefit Assessment

The current information on the investigational product is sufficient to justify the proposed clinical trial and ensure compliance with Good Clinical Practice. The potential benefits of conducting the trial are considered to outweigh the risks involved, provided that the study is carried out in accordance with the approved protocol, applicable local regulatory standards and ethical standards derived from the Declaration of Helsinki.

Conclusion

This will be an ongoing deliverable, as it is now legally mandated. All clinical trial evaluation reports generated by the National Drug Authority for clinical trial applications will be published on the website. The National Drug Authority acknowledges the support from Access Africa 2 and the European Union in achieving this milestone, which will ultimately enhance NDA's maturity level as a regulatory body.

